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BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

**REORDERING OF INTERNATIONAL
PRODUCTION CHAINS AND THE
NORWEGIAN CASE OF OFFSHORE MINING.**

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June 5th, 2024.

Policy Statement

Western countries intensify efforts to reduce dependence on international suppliers of critical inputs, especially in the mineral sector. Investment in local production, research & development of sustainable alternatives, and incentive policies are vital strategies. Initiatives such as the US-Norway Memorandum of Understanding and the Mineral Security Partnership (MSP) highlight the importance of international cooperation. However, it is essential to balance economic security and environmental responsibility, avoiding severe impacts, especially with the prospect of offshore mining on a commercial scale.

Background

The last decade has seen a trend by Western countries to reduce dependence on international suppliers of equipment and inputs considered essential for the functioning of their economies (Gaspar Filho and Santos, 2022). To increase economic security, mainly due to the Chinese market's strength in the sectors of critical raw or refined minerals, in addition to clean energy-generating equipment, a series of strategies were implemented by nations and companies. They seek to diversify sources of critical materials, such as minerals, semiconductors, and batteries, by investing in new production facilities in regions such as North America, Europe, and Western-aligned countries in other areas such as Southeast Asia.

Significant research and development efforts have been put into finding alternatives to these materials and improving recycling. Government policies, such as tax incentives and trade agreements, have also been implemented to promote diversification and encourage local production. However, the output of minerals necessary for the energy transition must comply with quality standards so that the environmental impacts of the activity are not as severe as those originated by an energy matrix based on hydrocarbons. Therefore, obtaining minerals from the ocean floor is still not an environmentally safe alternative, given the current state of technological development.

Aiming to strengthen production chains, a Memorandum of Understanding was signed between the United States (US) and Norway in April 2024 to deepen bilateral

cooperation in the critical minerals market. Representatives Daleep Singh (United States Deputy National Security Advisor for International Economics) and Jan Christian (Minister of Trade and Industry of Norway) state that both governments seek to promote high environmental and labor standards in global supply chains, also bypassing the external dependence that both countries have in the sector (United States of America, 2024). Relations between the two countries in the mineral field have deepened significantly over the past few years. In 2023, the Nordic country was welcomed by the Mineral Security Partnership (MSP), an initiative created by the USA to increase the security of the mineral market. Today, 14 countries seek to reduce their dependence on Chinese supplies (US Department of State, 2023).

The MSP, as of May 2024, is a comprehensive alliance of countries including Australia, Canada, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, India, Italy, Japan, Norway, the Republic of Korea, Sweden, the United Kingdom, United States, and the European Union (represented by the European Commission). The Partnership takes a holistic approach, considering projects across the clean energy production chain, from mining and extraction to secondary recovery, processing, refining, and recycling. Its focus on the supply chains of minerals and metals critical to clean energy technologies directly addresses four key areas: diversification and stabilization of global supply chains, investment, promotion of environmental, social, and governance standards, and increased recycling of critical minerals (US Department of State, 2023).

The European Critical Raw Materials Act, which came into effect in May 2024, plays a crucial role in ensuring a diversified, safe, and sustainable supply of critical raw materials for European industry (European Commission, 2024). It particularly secures inputs for key sectors such as clean energy, digitalization, defense, and aerospace. The Act's provisions are designed to support the European bloc's energy transition goals, including the REPowerEU plan. It's important to note that despite its alignment with the European bloc and the United States on international regimes, Norway is not a member of the European Union.

The deepening relations with Norway in the mineral field also appears to be due to the expectation of supplying critical mineral chains from resources extracted from the Norwegian Continental Shelf, which can cause severe environmental impacts. In January 2024, the country's Parliament approved the start.

of issuing scientific exploration licenses so that offshore commercial projects could be proposed later (Stallar, 2024). After diverging from the scientific community, international organizations, and the Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment due to the impacts it caused on the environment, an area of 281,000km² (approximately the size of Italy) was thus opened up for exploration on its continental shelf.

In the meantime, the American company UK Seabed Resources (UKSR), a subsidiary of the arms manufacturer Lockheed Martin, was sold to the Norwegian Loke Marine Minerals. While the United States has never ratified the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (1982) and cannot request exploration licenses from the International Seabed Authority, British projects had an American company in charge. UKSR holds two licenses in the Clarion-Clipperton Zone (CCZ) of the Pacific Ocean, a 4.5 million km² strip abundant in polymetallic nodules. The company also has a 19.9% share in Ocean Mineral Singapore, a subsidiary of Singapore's Keppel Corporation, licensed in the CCZ.

Findings

Of the aforementioned initiatives, only the European Critical Raw Materials Act provides that offshore mining projects will not be considered strategic by the European Commission until the adverse effects on the marine environment are correctly estimated. This would make it unlikely for projects dedicated to mining seabeds to benefit from investments from the European bloc, something based on the Precautionary Principle (European Parliament, 2024).

After the Norwegian Parliament's decision, the European Union spoke out against it. Although Norway is not part of the European bloc, the European Parliament published a resolution to express the bloc's collective concern regarding the activity to be initiated in Norwegian waters. They reiterate the importance of not issuing commercial exploration licenses until there is more data on environmental impacts available and reinforce the position of the European Commission and Member States in defending a moratorium against offshore mining based on the Precautionary Principle. Furthermore, they recall the obligations assumed by the Norwegian government when being part of different multilateral regimes (such as the Svalbard Treaty, the OSPAR Convention, the recent signing of the Treaty on Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdictions, and UNCLOS) and encourage Norway to follow collaborating with the European bloc through the Green Alliance signed in April 2023.

In addition to the position taken by the European Commission, 25 countries advocate a moratorium, precautionary pause, or even a ban on offshore mining. Are they:

Position	Countries (in chronological order)
Moratorium	Fiji, Palau, Samoa, Federated States of Micronesia (make up the Moratorium Alliance). New Zealand, Switzerland, Canada, United Kingdom and Mexico
Precautionary pause	Chile, Costa Rica, Ecuador, Spain, Germany, Panama, Vanuatu, Dominican Republic, Sweden, Ireland, Brazil, Finland, Portugal, Monaco and Denmark.
Ban	France.

In addition, state actors, companies, research associations, and environmental groups have also spoken out against offshore mining. The role of WWF-Norway stands out in suing the country's government due to the Norwegian Parliament's decision to open its Continental Shelf to mineral exploration. The environmental group claims there is no legal basis for issuing exploration licenses in the country's waters, and there are irregularities in the impact assessments conducted by the Ministry of Energy before Parliament's decision.

Conclusions

The journey to reduce dependence on international suppliers of critical inputs has led Western countries to adopt several strategies, especially in response to Chinese dominance in the sector. The energy transition mainly drives the growing demand for these resources. However, measures to reduce the environmental impacts resulting from an economy based on hydrocarbons must be designed so that the mineral industry's expansion is not harmful to the environment. Despite environmental concerns, the recent approval by the Norwegian Parliament to explore the country's Continental Shelf is an example of the challenges and controversies accompanying such initiatives.

International cooperation, as exemplified by the US-Norway Memorandum of Understanding and the creation of the Mineral Security Partnership (MSP), shows the

importance of alliances to ensure a stable and diverse supply of critical minerals. However, the European Critical Raw Materials Act and the European Union's demonstrations against offshore mining in Norwegian waters underline the need to balance economic security with environmental responsibility. The positions of several countries and organizations that defend moratoriums or even a ban on ocean mining reflect the growing concern about environmental impacts on the part of different actors. In this context, the policies and practices adopted must prioritize the diversification and security of resources and the preservation of the environment to guarantee sustainable development.

Recommendations

To promote a resilient and sustainable global economy, it is recommended that international and public policies prioritize the development of recycling technologies and substituting critical materials. Governments must invest substantially in research and development (R&D) to find viable alternatives to critical minerals and improve recycling processes. Furthermore, it is essential to implement tax incentives and subsidies for companies that adopt recycling practices and use alternative materials, reducing dependence on international suppliers and minimizing environmental impacts. Promoting multilateral trade agreements encouraging the sharing of technologies and best practices between nations can accelerate the transition to a more sustainable economy that is less dependent on single sources of critical minerals.

Furthermore, strict environmental standards must regulate the exploration and production of critical minerals. Creating an international regulatory framework stipulating sustainability and environmental protection criteria is imperative to avoid ecological damage. Mining projects, especially those involving offshore exploration, must be subject to transparent and robust impact assessments and should only be authorized after demonstrating environmental safety. Governments must adopt the Precautionary Principle, promoting moratoriums on new mining activities on the ocean floor until technology evolves to guarantee safe practices. Therefore, imports of mineral resources extracted from the seabed should not be considered in the short term. Additionally, international cooperation policies such as MSP must continue to promote environmental, social, and governance (ESG) standards, ensuring that critical minerals are produced and processed responsibly and sustainably.

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